

ECONOMIC AND MANAGERIAL INNOVATIONS IN THE ADMINISTRATION OF THE PORTFOLIO OF CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS OF THE DEVELOPER COMPANY: DIAGNOSTICS AND ASSESSMENT OF OPERATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY

Kishchak N.

Post-graduate student of the Department of Management in Construction,
Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, Ukraine
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7061509>

Abstract

The scientific hypothesis of the research adopted in the work determined that the dominant business trajectory of the processes of formation and administration of the portfolio of housing construction projects of the developer company (PHCP-DC) is the economic and organizational mechanism of interaction of the institutional participants of the projects. If the includes commercial housing construction projects, then the interaction of the developer company with other institutional participants of the project must take place in the format of joint investment institutes (in particular, CFF), which requires the presence of a manager of the housing construction fund (asset management company - AMC).

In accordance with the new concepts regarding the purpose of the operating system of the developer company (in the field of commercial housing construction), an analytical toolkit has been developed and substantiated, which corresponds to the format of the Eurocodes of BIM technologies, as well as to the procedures and indicators of regulation and evaluation of the operational activities of construction participants. which are defined by the International Financial Reporting System and National Accounting Standards (Regulations). Based on the phases of the investment and operational-production cycle of projects, the toolkit based on work is preventive, it should be attributed to the "pre-start project" stage (as part of the pre-investment phase) of the project. According to the final target orientation, the toolkit should predict the future results of the operational system of the developer enterprise, which implements projects as part of the PHCP-DC autonomous (within separate budgets, consolidated estimates and the institutional environment of the participants, subordinated to the AMC) strategic economic units and has and the structure of PHCP-DC to ensure both the greatest synergy (from the accepted alternative of combining individual projects into a single portfolio) and the lowest possible (in the circle of institutional participants and stakeholders) risk levels of implementing a housing construction investment program as part of several real projects.

Keywords: portfolio of housing construction projects of the developer company (PHCP-DC), asset management company (AMC), construction financing fund (CFF), strategic economic unit (SEU), functional and operational cycle (FOC), developer company (DC)

With the deployment of destructive processes in the economy, a significant slowdown in the pace of development in commercial residential construction is felt, which leads to numerous "long-term buildings" and significant financial losses for both enterprises participating in construction projects and individuals who were left without the expected housing.

In order to activate the market of commercial housing construction and overcome the situation when investments in housing construction become the riskiest type of business, and, first of all, to ensure the alignment of the economic interests of construction participants with the motivation of investors, one should turn to instrumental and analytical means of improving the operational activities of development companies. It is these companies, in the conditions of a decline in the activity of the investment market of commercial housing construction, that must ensure the growth of business activity in this segment of construction and overcome the urgent problems that accompany the business processes of the cycle of preparation, investment and construction of housing - destruction in the organization of investment and budgeting, violation of deadlines progress of construction, improper coordination of the interaction of the main participants (stakeholders) of construction [1-4].

Therefore, the issue of improving the scientific and methodological support for the activities of development companies in construction is on the agenda. The economic problems of forming a portfolio of projects for a developer company working in the field of commercial housing construction, which must coordinate the composition of the portfolio both with its own strategic priorities and with offers on the segment of the residential construction investment market that is promising for it, are practically ignored. In the future, to successfully integrate own administration activities for individual projects into a complete project portfolio and to coordinate these project activities with other institutional participants. Unresolved number of issues of operational activity of the developer company in the residential construction market during the formation and administration of a portfolio of projects in residential construction determines the scientific and applied orientation of this work [5].

The state of such an industry as housing construction is highly dependent on the existing construction financing system. According to statistics, about 60% of housing in Ukraine is built at the expense of public funds, up to 5% - at the expense of budget funds, about 1.5% - bank loans, the latter - means of enterprises of various forms of ownership. Construction investment

and the insecurity of investors during the last decades still remain problematic issues, which are not related to the complex regulation of these institutions and non-fulfillment (improper fulfillment) by the manager and/or developer of their obligations [6].

It is worth noting that according to Art. 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On Investment Activities", investment and financing of the construction of residential construction objects using non-state funds can be carried out exclusively through construction financing funds, real estate transaction funds, joint investment institutes, as well as by issuing targeted bonds.

Also, it would be worthwhile for the benefit of the investor to prescribe in detail in the law the norms regarding the change of an inefficient developer. The problem is that no one controls the double, triple sales schemes. The reputation of the builder plays a significant role here. However, currently in Ukraine, the developer's system folder (investment portfolio of the developer company) is opened only after the building is put into operation. Although, in fact, he can know all future project decisions at the stage when he has property rights and makes a sale. If the property rights to the apartment were immediately entered into the register of property rights after the sale, it would be impossible to sell this apartment a second time. It is only necessary to add this information to the register of property rights. It would be appropriate to supplement Art. 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On State Registration of Property Rights to Immovable Property and Their Encumbrances" (and other derivative norms) by the clause on state registration of property rights to acquire ownership of immovable property when investing in construction.

Therefore, the analysis of scientific, methodical and applied sources from the field and the subject of the study allowed us to reveal that the leading methodical and applied problem is the adaptation of the conceptual foundations of the "suit-to-built" development and methodical approaches regarding PHCP-DC to the realities of the commercial housing construction market, first of all, to the peculiarities of the economic interaction of construction project participants, when the developer company works under conditions of strict restrictions on the movement of financial funds from the side of the asset management company (ACM), which requires updating the approaches, content and algorithm of the developer's interaction with institutional

participants and stakeholders of construction projects housing, under the condition of consideration of projects as part of PHCP-DC as specific strategic economic units (SEU) of business. This, in turn, requires both a change in the system of indicators when evaluating projects regarding the expediency of their inclusion in the composition of PHCP-DC, and ensuring the developer's ability to formalize the ability to detect the impact of the progress of the project administration work in the portfolio on the financial results of its operational activities, the change in the value of its assets and the growth of the image as a leading stakeholder in the selected segment of the commercial residential construction market [7-11].

PHCP-DC is considered as a special property, economic-administrative and functional-technical complex, the components of which (residential buildings) require the organization of business processes for their administration in the format of a separate construction financing fund, headed by a separate manager. This manager (FCU) will be subordinated to the movement of cash and other assets of the project in the interaction system "developer-builder→FCU→minority investors (individuals, home buyers)".

Peculiarities of the organization of financing of commercial housing construction projects make it impossible to maneuver the resources of the builder and developer between different projects (as components of PHCP-DC), which requires autonomous administration of individual projects within the framework of a single operating system of the developer company.

The specified hypothesis provided the scientific basis for the modernization of the approach to the formation of the portfolio of construction projects of the developer company of the development company and the further implementation of the specified approach in the form of a practically configured methodological and analytical toolkit. formation of PHCP-DC (Table 1). The technology implemented in the work is a component of the functioning of the operating system of the developer company, as a result, it ensures the synergy of the results of the implementation of the specified portfolio for the developer company (which works as a leading stakeholder in several housing construction projects (in parallel or in series) as strategic economic units.

Table 1.

Content-process diagram of the toolkit for the formation and administration of a portfolio of construction projects

№	The name of the stage	№	Content and regulation of the stage, structured by its business elements
1.	The formation of applied prerequisites for the selection of proposals for the administration of commercial housing construction projects as SEU as part of the developer's project portfolio	1.1.	Initial ongoing study of the state and dynamics of external environmental factors in relation to construction development for housing construction projects, including the indirect influence of trends in the market of commercial housing construction and the possible effects of changes in the order of normative and regulatory activities of the organization of administration, financing, preparation, construction and commissioning of the product of projects - objects of housing construction.
		1.2.	The initial evaluation of the proposals of potential customers regarding the conclusion of contracts with this DC for the preparation and administration of the functional-operational cycle (FOC) of the project (s) in commercial residential construction - regarding the content of the tasks and duration of the FOC, the distribution of responsibilities and economic results for the intermediate and finished product of the project.
		1.3.	The primary analytical evaluation of the projects presented under clause 1.2., according to the system of analytical indicators, which is formalized for the needs of the DC, evaluates the economic, functional-technical, administrative-personnel and image characteristics of the DC's participation in each of the projects.
2.	Preparation and selection of PPBZh_DC alternatives in the format of a single visual-analytical model.	2.1.	Clarification (including involving the opinions of independent experts) of project characteristics, their coordination with potential customers.
		2.2.	Adoption of the final decision on the participation of DC as a leading stakeholder in housing construction projects as an SEU as part of the PHCP-DC
		2.3.	Formalized analytical presentation of the operating system of the DC as a system of interaction of the subsystems of the operating system of the DC (1- subsystem of development strategy and business planning; 2- subsystem of financial and resource-logistic support; 3 – subsystem of regulation) with local subsystems of administration of housing construction projects as strategic economic units and the administrative environment for the implementation of their projects, which is regulated by the AMC.
		2.4.	Development of options for synergistic arrangement of the content of cycles for individual projects.
		2.5.	Visual and graphic presentation of variants of a complete PHCP-DC.
		2.6.	Evaluation of variants of a complete PHCP-DC according to an innovative system of criteria, taking into account the evaluation of the reactions of the operational system of the DC as a project-adapted synergistic economic-administrative complex of the SEU. (description is given below)
3.	Adjustment of the operating system and organizational structure of the developer company to the content of the PHCP-DC implementation cycles	3.1.	Coordinating the composition of project administration work on the side of DC with other institutional participants - AMC, the customer and its co-investors.
		3.2.	Initial formation of the content of agreements between the developer company, institutional participants and stakeholders (executors) of the project.
		3.3.	Final coordination of agreements (contracts) that reflect the content and essence of the economic-administrative and functional interaction of the DC with the participants of the projects that are included in the PHCP-DC.
		3.4.	Implementation of the necessary economic, technological, information-analytical and organizational-administrative measures to adapt the current operating system and organizational structure of the company to the process of real implementation of projects (elements-SEU).
4.	Management of FOC projects as part of PHCP-DC	4.1.	Completion of project-estimating, organizational-technological, budgetary and management documentation for projects as part of PHCP-DC.
		4.2.	Implementation of projects. Operational adjustment of the completion of functional and operational cycles of projects. Intermediate budgetary and economic, technological and administrative control over the implementation of SEU projects
		4.3.	Assessment of the impact of the results of the implementation cycle of individual projects and the portfolio as a whole on financial results, the overall productivity of the DC operating system and the growth of its qualified assets.

During the formation of the toolkit, a number of scientific and methodological innovations were implemented regarding the economy and management of the operational activities of the developer company as a stakeholder of the project portfolio (investment and property complex).

1. In terms of the content and direction of the stages of formalized processing, selection of housing construction projects for the portfolio of the developer company and their subsequent productive implementation, this toolkit successfully combines: effective development platforms, with modern concepts of construction management and budgeting, and a productive information and analytical basis for decision-making in construction.

2. The toolkit has modernized the approach in evaluating construction projects as elements of SEU as part of the business portfolio (project portfolio) of the

$$R_{int}(m) = \sum_g \psi(g) * Rg; Rg = Z_g(m) / Z_g^{et}(m); Rg \leq 1; g=1-6; \quad (1)$$

$$Z_1(m) = NPV(m) / T^{ok}(m) = \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_{n-1}} [SP^{(+)}(m; t) / (1+\mu)^t] - \sum_{t=t_0}^{t_{n-1}} \{ [Bd(m; t) / (1+\mu)^t] \} / T^{ok}(m); t^0 < t^{si} < t^{un} < T^{ok} < T^{np} < T^{u3} \quad (2)$$

$$Z_2(m) = IDp(m) * IRR(m) \quad (3)$$

$$Z_3(m) = \sum_t QW^{ag}(m) / T_j = \sum_t [dReg^{NPV}_j(t) / dt] / T_j \quad (4)$$

$$Z_4(m) = 10000 / \sigma^2 \{ NPV(m) \} \quad (5); Z_5(m) = Y^{inv,act}_6 = 10000 / \sigma^2 \{ SP^{(+)}(m) \} \quad (6)$$

$$Z_6(m) = \sum_{k=1-3} \{ K_k / B^{k*k} \} \quad (7)$$

where

g - serial number of the indicator;

m - serial number of the project in the primary general list of projects that are subject to an initial assessment regarding the feasibility of their inclusion in the PHCP-DC composition;

Z₁(m) – the first indicator, calculated as the net consolidated (discounted) income of the project, weighted by the payback period of the project, million hryvnias/year; the growth of the indicator maximizes the volume and intensity of the project's profitability during all phases of the FOC of the project;

Z₂(m) - the second indicator, calculated by the product of the project's profitability index and the project's internal rate of return (in units); the growth of the indicator ensures a predominant growth of the project's income assets over the investor's liabilities, and, at the same time, minimizes the types of investment risk covered by the project's internal profitability, primarily inflationary, speculative and other types of industry and project risks;

Z₃(m) is an indicator of the current rate of growth of the project value, determined by the ratio of the sum of the ordinates of the current rate of growth of project assets to the total duration of the project cycle. The maximization of this indicator ensures an increase in the positive (income) intensity of the FOC project and the minimization of its negative (expenditure) part, promotes the selection of projects with a more rational structure of assets and a better correlation of the duration of the investment and operational phases of the cycle;

Z₄(m) is the fourth criterion that ensures the minimization of NPV variation, which is estimated through the root mean square deviation; in this way, the methodical and applied sequence of the stages of project

developer company. For the needs of the primary local assessment of the cycle of housing construction projects regarding the expediency (from the standpoint of the DC) of their inclusion in the composition of the PHCP-DC, a modernized system of R-indicators (1)-(4) was applied, which assess the competitiveness of the project as an investment object in the profitable commercial real estate, as well as the leading determinants of the stability of the functioning of the real estate customer and the investment object;

The indicated indicators are presented in a universal dimension (as a result of the correlation of local estimates of projects **Z₁(m)...** **Z₆(m)** according to these indicators with their statistically or imperatively determined exemplary counterparts **Z₁(m)...** **Z₆(m)** for the region and industry) and further - combined into the "integral indicator for assessing the economic reliability of the PHCP-DC cycle":

selection and the increase in the reliability of the obtained forecast project characteristics of PHCP-DC as a whole are ensured;

Z₅(m) - the fifth indicator - ensures the maximum reliability of the investment pre-selection of projects to the composition of PHCP-DC through the minimization of the root mean square deviation of the most difficult forecasted project variable - the net flow of income **SP⁽⁺⁾(m)**;

Z₆(m) - the sixth indicator, which provides the developer with a picture of the liquidity of assets and the solvency of the client company for the m-th project in terms of anti-bankruptcy for the client company; is calculated as the average share of the organization's net working capital in the total amount of its sources for the last 3 years for the customer enterprise;

Rg(m) - relative assessments of the project according to the indicators, determined by the ratio of the actual values according to the indicators **Zg(m)** to their exemplary (reference) values **Zg(m)**, which are determined by the developer based on the results of the market evaluation of investments in commercial residential construction;

Rg(m) is an integral indicator of assessing the economic reliability of the housing construction project cycle;

ψ(g) - coefficients of the specific weight of the values in the integral indicator **Rint(m)**; are determined through the ranks of indicators established by expert heuristics;

t - number of the current period of project cycle implementation (month); **T_{ok}(m)** the payback period of the project;

T_c - with the estimated life cycle duration;

t_{un} - the time of the start of net income (net cash flow) for the project, counting from the moment of the start of the cycle (**t₀**);

$t_{3,i}$ – the time of completion of investment, counting from the moment of the beginning of the cycle (t_0);

Tpr - the term of exiting the estimated project capacity (according to the directive level of achieving a certain volume of housing sales);

NPV(m) - net present value (net discounted income) of the project, determined for the estimated duration of the cycle T_r, t_s ;

Bd(m,t) - the amount of investment costs determined for a separate t-current period (according to the investment budget, the consolidated estimate and the resource-calendar investment development plan)

Bd(m,t)/(1+μ)t – similar value to **Bd(m,t)**, but discounted (consolidated) at the beginning of the cycle of the mth project;

SP(+)(m;t) is the volume of the net flow of income for a separate t-current period (during the operational phase, which for projects of this type lasts from the beginning of sales to their completion, and may partially occur in parallel with the investment phase of the cycle), for projects of this content are determined by the current difference: net proceeds from housing sales and all operating costs of the operational phase (including both costs for servicing sales and costs for administration of this flow from the side of DC and AMC);

SP(+)(m;t)/(1+μ)t - similar value to **SP(+)(m;t)**, but discounted (consolidated) at the beginning of the cycle of the mth project;

$\Sigma t = t_0 - t_{3,i} \{ [Bd(m,t)/(1+μ)t] \}$ - the sum of discounted investment volumes for the entire duration of sales calculated by the accumulated total;

$\Sigma t = t_{CH} - T_{U,3} [SP(+)(m;t)/(1+μ)t]$ - calculated by the accumulated total, the amount of the net income stream discounted at the current moment of the cycle, million hryvnias.

IDp(m) is the project profitability index, determined by the ratio $\Sigma t = t_0 - t_{3,i} \{ [Bd(m,t)/(1+μ)t] \}$ to $\Sigma t = t_{CH} - T_{U,3} [SP(+)(m;t)/(1+μ)t]$

RegNPVj(t) - a function established by regression (polynomial of the 5th degree), which models the distribution of the net combined income NPV for the given m project;

dRegNPVj(t)/dt - the first derivative of the **RegNPVj(t)** function at time t;

QWag(m) - current growth rate cheap cost of the mth project;

The indicated final indicator and the simple percentage interpretation scale corresponding to it provide grounds both for revealing the comparative advantages of the project among other analogues (potential SEU), and for making a decision regarding the feasibility of its inclusion in the PHCP-DC composition.

The defining scientific and methodical innovations of the tools introduced in the work are:

a) the adaptability of the toolkit for the formation of the PHCP-DC to the specifics of the implementation of commercial housing construction projects and the corresponding need for a multi-faceted consideration of the elements of the DC portfolio in terms of:

- strategic economic units of the economic portfolio of the developer's enterprise;

- a temporary enterprise that, during the pre-investment (preparatory) and investment (construction)

phases of the operational and production cycle of projects, is subordinate to the environment of institutional participants headed by the AMC;

- the resource-property, economic-administrative and operational-production complex of investment and construction facilities (within the framework of the autonomous budget for each of the projects, the summary estimate and the resource-calendar plan), according to which the developer administers the content of business processes (resource- logistical support; preparation, administration and control; construction; implementation).

b) meaningful, methodical and calculation-analytical adaptation of the toolkit to European development standards, the international financial reporting system and modern project administration technologies. With the use of the indicated means of visualization, justification, unification and standardization of decision-making, which was implemented by the toolkit through a fundamentally new operational structuring - production cycle – the toolkit offers options for subsystems and elements for organizational structures of project administration (both within the operating system of the developer company and at the level of near-object structures) and provides analytical support for the development of a construction project for the construction of housing as a separate strategic economic unit as part of the PHCP-DC during the entire duration of the operational and production cycle - from the approval of the development agreement to the termination of this agreement (completion of the interaction of the DC with the customer, subcontractors, AMC and other stakeholders and the achievement of the target longing for the project as an object of commercial residential construction.

c) realized by the economic and analytical components of the toolkit, the capacity of productive modeling of project cycles as part of PHCP-DC and the subsequent manifestation of their impact on the growth of productivity of the developer enterprise, identified and evaluated through:

- an increase in the success of the operating system of the developer enterprise, in particular, an increase in financial results from the main activity; an increase in the value, structure of sources and resources of the return of its assets;

- improvement of the administration system of the development company at all its levels, divisions and elements of the organizational structure, as a result of which there is a significant increase in its image as an administrator and leading stakeholder of commercial housing construction projects.

As evidenced by the implementation of the work in the practice of development and construction and investment companies working in the field of commercial housing construction, the defining applied advantage of the toolkit introduced in the work is the possibility of successful formalized administration and adjustment of the parameters of the operational and production cycles of projects as part of the PHCP-DC with economic requirements dictated by: articles of the capital and operating budgets; sections of the consolidated estimate, the

content of the works performed (assigned by the sub-contractors of the development project) and the directives of the asset management company.

The functional and product specifics of commercial housing construction projects and the features of mandatory regulation of the course of their execution cycle from the side of the asset management company - make it impossible to use traditional ideas, approaches and applied tools for the formation of a business portfolio to the needs of this study. On the basis of such an analysis, an urgent need for a fundamental update of the methodical approach regarding the content and operational technology of the processes of forming PHCP-DC has been determined - in the direction of introducing and substantiating the modernized toolkit of forming PHCP-DC as a specific business portfolio for the developer enterprise.

The methodological and applied basis of the research was chosen, the basis of which was laid: modern construction development platforms, "management by goals", productive concepts of budgeting and the synthesis of applied tools of economic-analytical and economic-diagnostic decision-making tools, which made it possible to build an updated system of indicators of the functioning of the operational system of the DC through the prism of implementation of operational and production cycles of projects.

References:

1. Kulikov, P., Ryzhakova, G., Honcharenko, T., Ryzhakov, D., Malykhina, O. (2020). OLAP-tools for the formation of connected and diversified production and project management systems. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 8(10), 7337–7343. <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijatcse/2020/254952020>
2. Akselrod, R., Shpakov, A.i, Ryzhakova, G., T., Honcharenko Integration of Data Flows of the Construction Project Life Cycle to Create a Digital Enterprise Based on Building Information Modeling *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering* 2022 Vol 12(1) pp. 40-50. DOI: 10.46338/ijetae0122_05
3. T. Honcharenko, Y. Chupryna, I. Ivakhnenko, M. Zinchenco and T. Tsyfra. —Reengineering of the Construction Companies Based on BIM-technology, *International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, 8(8), August 2020, pp. 4166-4172. <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijeter/2020/22882020>
4. T. Honcharenko, O. Terentyev, O. Malykhina, I. Druzhynina, I. Gorbatyuk. (2021). BIM-Concept for Design of Engineering Networks at the Stage of Urban Planning. *Int. Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, 11(5):1306- 1312, <http://insightsociety.org/ojaseit/index.php/ijaseit/article/view/13687>
5. Mihaylenko V., Honcharenko T., Chupryna K., Liazschenko T. (2021). Integrated processing of spatial information based on multidimensional data models for general planning tasks. *International Journal of Computing*, vol. 20 (1), 55—62. <https://doi.org/10.47839/ijc.20.1.2092>
6. D. Ryzhakov, O. Dikiy, M. Druzhynin, H. Petrenko, T. Savchuk. (2020). Innovative tools for management the lifecycle of strategic objectives of the enterprise-stakeholder in construction. *International Journal on Emerging Trends in Engineering Research*, 8(8), pp. 4526-4532. <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijeter/2020/78882020>
7. T. Honcharenko, G. Ryzhakova, Ye. Borodavka, D. Ryzhakov, V. Savenko, O. Polosenko. Method for representing spatial information of topological relations based on a multidimensional data model, *ARPJ Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, vol. 16, Issue 7, 2021, pp. 802-809, http://www.arpjournals.org/jeas/research_papers/rp_2021/jeas_042_1_8555.pdf
8. Ishchenko T., Chupryna, Y., Pokolenko, V. (2018). The organization of biosphere compatibility construction: Justification of the predictors of building development and the implementation prospects. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (UAE)*, 2018, 7(3), pp. 545–549.
9. Tormosov, R., Chupryna, I., Ryzhakova, G., Pokolenko V., Prykhodko, D., Faizullin, A. (2021). Establishment of the rational economic and analytical basis for projects in different sectors for their integration into the targeted diversified program for sustainable energy development. *SIST 2021 - 2021 IEEE International Conference on Smart Information Systems and Technologies*, 9465993.
10. Ryzhakova, G. M. and Leshchinska, I. V. Evaluation of the productivity of the developer's operating system in the microenvironment of housing construction stakeholders [Electronic resource] Ways to increase the efficiency of construction in the conditions of the formation of market relations. - 2019. - Issue 42. - pp. 120–131. DOI: 10.32347/2707-501x.2019.42.120-131
11. Honcharenko, T., Mihaylenko, V., Borodavka, Y., Dolya, E., Savenko, V. (2021) Information tools for project management of the building territory at the stage of urban planning. In: *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, vol. 2851, pp. 22–33.